

THE USE OF NON-TRADITIONAL FORMS OF MATHEMATICS LESSONS AS A MEANS OF INCREASING INTEREST IN THE SUBJECT

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Abstract: The article highlights the role of using new innovative technologies to improve the effectiveness of the education system.

Keywords: Lesson, traditional, classical, frontal lessons, laboratory work.

Аннотация: В статье освещены роль, использовании новых инновационных технологий повышения эффективности системы образования.

Ключевые слова: Урок, традиционным, классическим, фронтальным уроки, лабораторная работа.

INTRODUCTION

One of the main requirements for educators today is to get out of the "uniformity" mold when taking classes, look for new unconventional lesson methods, put existing new methods into practice, increase students' interest in science, the profession, teach independent use of additional literature and guide them to conscious acquisition of knowledge. Educational processes in educational institutions in our country are manifested in the following manifestations.

Innovation in the educational process of a modern teacher should be able to use and implement approaches. In the process, the following requirements are imposed on future teachers:

- knowledge of the concept of innovation in education, its essence;
- knowledge of the role and role of innovation technologies in the implementation of the educational goal;
- knowledge of the principles of application of innovative technologies in the sciences;
- be able to organize a non-traditional lesson on the basis of integration;
- knowledge of ways to organize and ensure independent activities of students;

- to conduct training sessions of non-educational imitation using advanced pedagogical technologies;

- must know and master the activating methods of Education.

Non-traditional lessons are one of the forms of organization of education and training of schoolchildren. Such lessons bring school education closer to life and reality, so students really like them. Children are willing to participate in such classes, as they need to show not only their knowledge, but also their creative abilities.

The importance of non-traditional lessons in the general educational process is primarily due to the fact that educational activity itself, aimed in its traditional sense at the assimilation by the student body as a whole of the requirements of the basic school curriculum, not adequately associated with creative activity, can lead to inhibition of intellectual development of children.

The introduction of non-traditional teaching methods into the primary school curriculum aims to expand the educational process and, without breaking away from the problems of education and upbringing, develop the personal qualities of the child.

Thus, non-traditional forms of education are an interesting, unusual form of providing material in the classroom. It is the use of non-traditional forms of education that activates the thinking processes of younger schoolchildren, encourages them to constantly search creatively, teaches them to analyze information, build a coherent logical statement, communicate with each other, correctly express their point of view, and tolerate the opinion of another person. Non-traditional methods are thus aimed at creating a favorable motivational and emotional background in the lesson, which leads to the development of a sustained interest in its mastery.

Everyone knows that we are currently living in an information society. This also affects our children and students. As a result of total computerization, schoolchildren have lost interest in reading and in the book as such. This led to the fact that students actually stopped reading educational literature, as a result: the culture of monologue speech decreased, the level of comprehension of what they read decreased. That is why teachers are forced to use non-traditional forms of teaching. Thus, Poincare's catch phrase that the subject of mathematics is so serious that it does not hurt to make it at least a little entertaining is only partially true. Therefore, a modern teacher who loves her profession is required to find a way to the hearts of her students so that they are interested in every lesson. It depends on the pedagogical skills and the use of new innovative

technologies of the teacher in teaching traditional, classical, frontal lessons using conference lessons, seminar lessons, laboratory work, thematic games. This was largely facilitated by familiarity with the rich experience of teachers. In addition, educational processes are being modernized.

Constant changes in curricula, assignments and requirements have led to some "nervousness" of participants in the educational process. That is why a variety of non-traditional forms of teaching mathematics lessons contribute not only to increasing interest in the subject, improving the quality of education, but also are elements of "relaxation", improving the microclimate in the classroom and improving vitality.

It is advisable to conduct a lesson conference as a repetitive generalization, and this can be done both after any particular topic and after studying several topics (based on residual knowledge). To conduct a lesson, the class students can be divided into groups. For each group, formulate the topic of the report, strictly regulate the time of the report, and otherwise provide complete freedom of action. This will allow students to make computer presentations of their reports, to involve weak students in performances, who will certainly be given a good grade for their performance, since the assessment of the entire group is given collectively according to the participation of each student. Undoubtedly, the team will make any disadvantaged student learn the proposed report by checking it repeatedly, explaining and asking often in a way that the teacher will not ask. After the reports, that is, the plenary session within the framework of the lesson, it is necessary to conduct the problematic part of the lesson, that is, to prepare the practical part, where students put into practice their existing knowledge and skills.

Usually, after the conference, I allocate a lesson to summarize the results, further consolidate the knowledge gained, and then give a test paper. According to the statistics I have given, the results of such a control are twenty percent higher than in the usual form of studying the material.

Seminars can be held both to introduce new concepts, acquire new knowledge, broaden horizons, and to discuss problematic issues. An example of the first type of seminar is, for example, the discussion of paragraphs marked with icons. The second type is, for example, a discussion of various ways to prove the Pythagorean theorem, or such an urgent problem as transcendental equations reduced to quadratic ones, which can be submitted to the seminar at the final repetition of the course.

The lesson is laboratory work. Laboratory work in mathematics can be carried out starting from 5th grade. In such lessons, children learn to draw conclusions, confirm or refute hypotheses, and set up experiments. Laboratory work in mathematics prepares students for this type of work and teaches them how to properly design work in physics and chemistry.

The following laboratory work can be carried out:

1. Finding the arithmetic mean.
2. Finding the light area of the room.
3. Finding the steepness of the steps.
4. Finding the useful volume of air, etc.

Geometric material fits well into laboratory work. For example, on the topic of "Polygon areas", you can make very interesting works. Before starting to plot graphs using a derivative, you can conduct laboratory work that allows you to generalize knowledge about the intervals of monotony and extremes of the function. From my point of view, it is laboratory work that allows students to "hold on to mathematics with their hands" and help answer the age-old question of young pragmatists: "Why do we need this?"

The lesson is a game. This type of lesson is a good way to diversify the study of "boring topics". But here the teacher must show creativity in order to come up with a game. For example, fairy tale lessons. The results are simply fantastic: students enthusiastically solve examples with fractions of 10 to 13 actions. Fairy tale lessons such as "The Tale of the Unit", or "The Tale of Geometric Shapes", or "The Tale of the Angle Bisector", take place "in one go" and have consistently positive results. "Square Root Games". A special place is occupied by the lessons of the game "Sea Battle", where two flotillas participate and, having projectiles, sink enemy ships. The study of the history of brave ships and naval symbols give the lesson romance and connection with life. Students play "Sea Battle" with passion. Lessons – games "Christmas tree, light up!" before the new year, both "Smart Guys and smart girls" create an additional festive atmosphere in mathematics and inspire confidence in the success of learning, they are also lessons that instill interest in the subject. Such lessons involve a lot of preparation on the part of the teacher. Of course, each teacher uses his own methodological techniques, best practices, and approaches to building lessons, which at the same time each of us constantly learns by himself. Well, that's our wonderful profession.: be open to learning new techniques, be ready to exchange opinions and have a constructive dialogue with each other and with students.

Expanding the scope of the introduction of new pedagogical and information technologies into the educational process, applying advanced experience in this direction, drawing up and implementing specific plans in this area in each subject, electronic textbooks and teaching aids and programs and lecture texts such as moving to floppy disks, achieving the provision of each student with them, achieving a wide introduction of modern pedagogical and information technologies in scientific and scientific and methodological work, as well as in the educational process, providing the educational system with the necessary information tools, linking educational institutions to communication networks important tasks are considered.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it is important to organize modern education at the level of World requirements, improve with the help of information communication tools, apply Active educational methods in non-traditional lessons in improving the effectiveness of the educational process. This will make students have an interest in learning the basics of science, develops skills working on independent literature, increases the effectiveness of education, involving in the search for solutions to issues and problems.

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